

Assessing the Impact of English Writing Proficiency on Academic Performance: A CEFRL-Based Study of CA Students

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Abstract

This research article delineates the impact of writing proficiency in English on the academic performance of Chartered Accountancy students. The research study has considered the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFRL) to assess and evaluate the data collected for this research. The participants involved were selected through the convenience sampling technique. Subsequently, the data collected has been analyzed through the qualitative content analysis to ascertain the writing proficiency of students in English, as guided by the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFRL). This research finds out that the students with high and intermediate level of writing skills were found performing relatively better in their academics as compared to those who had had a low level of writing skills. The study concludes that there is a robust relationship between the writing proficiency in English and the academic performance of the Chartered Accountancy students.

Keywords

CEFRL, Chartered Accountancy, Academic Performance, English, Writing Proficiency

Introduction and Background to the Study

The English language is one of the world's most popular languages and known to be a *Lingua Franca* in numerous countries across the globe. It happens to be one of the main languages of international communication as it has acquired the status of a global language (Crystal, 1997). In the context of the Indian subcontinent before the creation of Pakistan, the British government imposed the English Language as the means of communication. This helped them maintain their hegemony over the native people. However, this in turn left an indelible mark on society itself. The impact was so long-lasting that even after centuries of struggle against the colonizers and then securing independence, the language still has not lost its status in the society. On the contrary, it secured a firm space in society. It is the primary language of instruction in educational institutes with different names and purposes, since learning and publishing in it is taken as the "necessary sin" among all academic circles.

This study aims to assess the impact of English writing proficiency on the academic performance of Chartered Accountancy (CA) students. By examining the influence of English language skills on various aspects of academic performance, such as writing skills and overall educational attainment, this research seeks to shed light on the significance of English writing proficiency in relation to academic performance.

Problem Statement

The considerable proficiency in writing English is deemed inevitable in the present era due to the dominant and prestigious nature of the English language in the education sector worldwide. On a similar note, the Chartered Accountancy needs a high level of English proficiency to yield desired academic achievements. However, despite the professional and academic importance of English language in the nook and corners of the world, there has not been much research carried out in

Pakistan studying the impact of English writing proficiency on the academic performance of Chartered Accountancy (CA) students. Moreover, in the current studies related to English language proficiency, there is also a dearth of addressing the importance of writing skills to attain educational achievement. Therefore, the given study delves deeply to unearth the English writing proficiency and its impact on the academic performance of Chartered Accountancy (CA) Students.

Research Objectives

1. To examine the ways in which the specific errors in English grammar components, and adherence to the content organization, argumentation, and coherence in English writing, impact the academic performance of Chartered Accountancy (CA) students

Research Questions

1. How do the specific errors in English grammar components, and adherence to the content organization, argumentation, and coherence in English writing, impact the academic performance of Chartered Accountancy (CA) students?

Significance of Study

The significance of the study cannot be overstated since every student in an educational field is concerned about the level of their English writing proficiency because none of the academic achievements is possible without it. This study can be deduced as beneficial for institutions and teachers who make education policies, this in turn can provide students with teaching support, and language assistance through workshops and various communicative activities.

Delimitation of the Study

This research only focuses on the English writing proficiency of Chartered Accountancy (CA) students. Instead of thoroughly exploring the impact of other factors of language on academic performance, this research is only limited to assessing the impact by keeping in mind the writing skills proficiency. However, there is a lot of space to explore other factors involved in English proficiency to help readers understand the role of other levels of English on academic performance.

Literature Review

The importance of the English writing proficiency caters as a necessity particularly in educational institutes, where English is the language of instruction. Thus, the purpose of this study is to assess the English writing proficiency and its impact on the academic performance of Chartered Accountancy (CA) students. Consequently, the ability to effectively communicate in written form in English significantly influences academic performance. This Review of the literature includes discussion which is entailed with recent researches in English language proficiency to justify the gap and pave the way for the given study.

To begin with, in several quantitative research, the importance of English proficiency for students studying abroad at English-medium institutions, especially for those whose first language is not English has been discussed (Li et al., 2010). The results conclude that the ability of overseas students to successfully complete their studies is strongly determined by their level of English proficiency. In addition, several cross-cultural and culture-specific issues, such as academic culture shock brought by the differences in the educational system, delivered lectures, and relationships between students and teachers, can be enlisted as key factors that affect the academic success of international students (Li et al., 2010). These elements must be considered to guarantee that overseas students have the chance to succeed academically and providing them with the right resources and support can help them overcome the difficulties they encounter as students.

In addition, (Ying Zheng et al., 2016) investigated the use of a common European framework of reference for languages in the assessment of writings in English in China. They employed a mixed method approach to study the relevant topic in detail. They selected 20 ELT teachers, 120 students and 09 CEFR experts. All the students were from non-English majors in Wuhan University, China. This study also employed survey techniques to study the Chinese English language teacher's expertise in CEFR. It was also identified that CEFR had no official authorization, and the students were not able to write even 250 words in English. Moreover, after assessment of the writings through CEFR, it was found that those students who were in the 1st study year had average high scores as compared to the 2nd and 3rd year students in essay writings evaluated by the Chinese ELT teachers. However, (Ying Zheng et al., 2016) emphasis on the need of research that collects larger data to fully understand this concept.

Additionally, in a recent study conducted by (Al Busaidi, 2017) the relationship between ELP, gender, college, and academic efficiency was investigated. The test scores and GPAs of 857 undergraduate students from three groups in consecutive years (2010, 2011 and 2012), at Sultan Qaboos University (SQU) situated in Oman, were taken into considerations for this research that developed the researcher on profound indications regarding the correlation between English language proficiency and academic success, with language proficiency accounting for 13.5% of the variance in academic performance. The study also identified the influence of gender and college on achievement. The combined factors of language proficiency, college, and gender were found to predict 24% of students' success, with gender exhibiting the strongest predictive effect.

Moreover, in a quantitative correlative study by (Ezeudu, 2021) which was conducted among secondary students in Nigeria, the relationship between English proficiency and academic achievement was examined. The study findings revealed a significant positive correlation between English proficiency and academic performance in English, biology, government, and mathematics. The outcomes hold potential gain for researchers working in contexts where English is used as a second language. It sheds light on the importance of English proficiency in academic achievement among students and contributes to the understanding of language's role as a facilitator of learning in such contexts.

Furthermore, another study in this regard was carried out by (Sun et al., 2021) who investigated the relationship between the second language English writing self-efficacy and achievements. The main purpose of the research study was to explore the average size effect of writing self-efficacy and writing achievements for first and second language writers. Besides, the other main aim of the researchers was to examine the ways writings in L1 and L2 moderate the relationship based on the meta-analysis of the journals articles and dissertations. The research study made use of 565 effect sizes from 76 studies through data coding, screening and literature searches. The research study found that there was a moderate relationship ($r=.29$) between the writing performance and the writing confidence. It shows that there was 9% variability associated with the students self-efficacy and the English writing achievements. Besides, writing in English as L1/L2 was found to moderate the relationship between the writing self-efficacy and the writing achievement with the effect size of ($r=.441$) in L2 learners, which is significant as compared to ($r=.233$) in the L1 learners. This was brought forth after controlling the gender, sample size, grades and the publication types and statistical procedures.

Besides, all these research studies that have been conducted to explore the relationship between English language proficiency and academic achievement, particularly in the context of intensive language study; the results of these studies have been inconclusive. Therefore, further research is warranted to establish a more precise definition of the key concept involved. Such research endeavors have the potential to provide valuable insights for program planners and curriculum designers, enabling them to develop more targeted and effective language programs that foster enhanced academic outcomes.

Research Methodology

The methodology section of this research focuses on outlining the approach and techniques used to assess the English writing proficiency and its impact on the academic performance of students of Chartered Accountancy (CA). This section provides a detailed description of research design, participant selection, and data analysis employed in this study.

Research Design

According to (Trochim, 2006) the research design is made up of the comprehensive strategy the researcher utilizes to successfully combine numerous study components in a coherent and logical way. It provides a guide for gathering, measuring, and analyzing data, ensuring that the research problem is properly handled. It is important to note that the type of design should be determined by the research problem, rather than the design dictating the choice of the research problem. The researcher has used qualitative research design in this study, which has made it easier to analyze data, and create a thorough comprehension of the subject matter. With the aid of this layout, the observation of events was done in their unfiltered and natural settings, offering a genuine viewpoint.

Sampling

In this research, participants were chosen based on their relevant knowledge and information pertaining to the research topic. The choice of convenience sampling was made due to its ease and

freedom in conducting data analysis, and its flexibility in selecting participants. In this study, specifically six students of English at Prerequisite Competencies level, from a private educational institution, namely, *School of Business and Management, Rawalpindi, Pakistan*, who had studied the subject of writing and comprehension skills in detail with types of sentences, parts of speech, tenses, different types of essays including argumentative essay, comprehension passages, precis writing, and letter writing were selected using the said technique. These students were given a writing task which consisted of an argumentative essay of about 200 words. The reason for assigning an argumentative essay was that it requires a lot of competence and language expertise to present arguments and opinions in a logical manner to justify the stance. Afterwards, the responses of the participants were thoroughly examined as part of the research analysis.

Data Collection Tools

This study opted for a textual data collection tool to collect the data in written form and then analyse the written responses separately. The utilization of written tasks proved to be highly beneficial for this research, as it produced a comprehensive understanding and data collection for the research topic.

Theoretical Framework

In the given research study, the researcher has incorporated the *Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR)*, as a theoretical framework. Basically, this framework was presented in the 1990s by the Council of Europe, which talks about the English language proficiency of students. It has bifurcated the criteria for evaluating levels of proficiency in multiple categories including, reading, writing, speaking and listening. Besides, it has elaborated proficiency from the basic use of English to the advanced usage of English by the participants involved. On the other hand, it has also provided the criteria for ascertaining the precise proficiency of the students. As this research only deals with the English writing proficiency, so the criteria given for it by CEFR involves the interpretation and categorization of data in order to ascertain the English writing proficiency level manifested in the written task. As per CEFR, the writing task given for evaluating proficiency may include letters, reports and essays.

Moreover, the written task will be evaluated by keeping the following criteria in mind if it is argumentative:

1. Grammar
2. Content Organization
3. Argumentation
4. Coherence

Data Analysis Tools

Qualitative content analysis was employed in this study as a suitable method to analyze the data. Qualitative content analysis is a qualitative data analysis technique that involves careful analysis of the textual and visual features of the data set to draw certain meanings and patterns, thus contributing to drawing specific conclusions. The content of the participants' responses in this research was analyzed facilitating the arrangement of a conclusive analysis. Qualitative content analysis proved to be an efficient and straightforward approach compared to other data analysis methods because it provides accurate means for examination. In the current research, the data was analyzed by bearing in mind the linguistic features to unearth the level of English writing proficiency under the umbrella of the *Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR)*.

Data Analysis

Academic performance of a student is entailed with the levels of success of a student, teacher or institution that is achieved in meeting their educational goals as indicated by their summative and formative assessment and GPA (Talib & Sansgiry, 2012). This study acknowledges the scope of English language writing proficiency in the educational sector and therefore, it adds to the existing literature by exploring English language writing proficiency and its impact on academic performance of Chartered Accountancy (CA) students.

Grammar

Grammar is one of the important components when it comes to writing in any language. The correct use of grammar is inevitable to reach the desired conclusion, and to communicate thoughts to other people properly. In the given data, the grammar usage is analyzed as per the instructions of the *Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR)* under different categories as identified after a thorough analysis of the written responses.

Punctuation and Orthographic Errors

These are the essential components in English writing. The misuse of them may even alter the entire meaning. Using correct spellings and punctuation marks manifest command over the English language. However, many of the participants were found struggling with the correct use of punctuation and orthography.

For instance,

1. *When more people are educated it leads to more prod.* (Participant A, 2023).
2. *When people are educated they can contribute to industries, business and overall growth of economy.* (Participant A, 2023).
3. *By equipping individuals with necessary skills and knowledge we can build a skilled workforce, faster innovation, increase productivity, reduce poverty and drive social and economic development* (Participant A, 2023).
4. *If the literacy rate is increased then the agriculture sector is also improved.* (Participant B).
5. *To begin one can argue that a literate population forms the foundation for a skill workforce, driving innovation and productivity.* (Participant D, 2023).
6. *Additionally literacy empowers individual to participate more actively in the economy.* (Participant D, 2023).
7. *In conclusion the relationship between a nation's economic prosperity and its level of literacy is undeniable.* (Participant D, 2023).
8. *Do their jobs with more efficiency and less wastage of resource* (Participant F, 2023).

Here in the above sentences, as per the grammar, there should have been the use of a comma after “educated” in first two sentences, and “knowledge”, “increased”, “begin”, “additionally” and “in conclusion” in the third, fourth, fifth, sixth and seventh sentence. Moreover, the participants didn’t use periods after “development” in the third and eighth sentence.

Moreover, there is also an error of punctuation in the writing of the other participants. Such as,

9. *People use their knowledge and skills in respective industries and fields which increases the revenues of the country.* (Participant E, 2023).
10. *It cause the industries to flourish which in return lead to improve standard of living of the country* (Participant F, 2023).
11. *Economic prosperity of the country is also depends upon the political stability which comes from literacy.* (Participant F, 2023).

In the ninth sentence, a comma should be placed after the word “field” to make it more readable. Moreover, a comma after “flourish” and a period should be placed after “country” in the tenth sentence. In the eleventh sentence, the comma should be placed before and after “which.”

On the other hand, the study also found orthographic errors in the writings of the participants. Spellings play an important role in conveying the proper sense of any sentence or word. If the spellings are incorrect, there are chances that the meanings would be interpreted in a wrong manner.

For instance,

1. *Prosperous.* (Participant F, 2023).
2. *Jobe* (Participant F, 2023),
3. *Knowledgeable* (Participant F, 2023).
4. *Fuctual* (Participant F, 2023).
5. *Individual* (Participant D, 2023).

The above given spellings are wrong in all the examples. The revised spellings would be “prosperous”, “job”, “knowledgeable”, “factual”, and “individual.”

Errors in the Articles, Possessive Pronouns, Subject-Verb Agreement Usage

Additionally, there are mistakes of the article usage, possessive pronouns as well as subject-verb agreement in the written excerpts. For example,

1. *More the level of literacy, more it raise the economy.* (Participant B, 2023).
2. *Education also play a role in reducing poverty.* (Participant D, 2023).
3. *A literate population is more likely to break the cycle of poverty as individual gain.*

- (Participant D, 2023).
4. *Education contribute to improve health outcomes.* (Participant D, 2023).
 5. *Other factor such as natural resources and political stability.* (Participant D, 2023).
 6. *Literacy act as catalyst, amplifying impact of these factor.* (Participant D, 2023).
 7. *Literacy empower individuals.* (Participant D, 2023).
 8. *Creating a ripple effect that positively impact the nation's overall well being.* (Participant D, 2023).
 9. *Economic prosperity is directly relates to the literacy rate of the country.* (Participant E, 2023).
 10. *People with education when comes to power, they also aware of their responsibilities.* (Participant E, 2023).
 11. *Economic development of country.* (Participant B, 2023).
 12. *In such society.* (Participant E, 2023).
 13. *People grow with different point of view.* (Participant E, 2023).
 14. *Economy grow rapidly.* (Participant E, 2023).
 15. *With respect to others views and peace.* (Participant E, 2023).
Here, there should be “raises”, “plays”, “individuals gain”, “contributes”, “other factors”, “acts and factors”, “empowers”, “impacts”, “related” and “are also aware”, instead of the words used in the above sentences, as the subjects must agree with the verbs in English grammar. Whereas “a” should be used before “country” in the eleventh sentence, and “a” should be used before “society” in the twelve sentence. Moving on, there is also an error of subject-verb agreement in the thirteenth sentence where “point of view” is used instead of “points of views” to make the subject agree with the verb. Moreover, the word “grow” should be changed to “grows” to maintain subject verb agreement in the fourteenth sentence. On the other hand, there is an error of possessive pronoun usage in the fifteenth sentence. There should be the addition of the apostrophe ‘s’ in the word “others”. So, the revised version becomes “others’.” Adding to the same idea, the sentence sixteenth lacks proper article usage as per the English grammar.
 16. *People in countries with high literacy rate.* (Participant E, 2023).
The proper usage will be “with a high literacy rate”, in the above given sentence.
 17. *Fulfil all their duties and responsibilities which have positive impact on their society.* (Participant E, 2023).
 18. *It also compel people to think out of the box.* (Participant F, 2023).
 19. *It is the literacy rate that make any country prosperous.* (Participant F, 2023).
 20. *It not only lead to economical prosperity but also advance the country in technological term.*(Participant F, 2023).
 21. *It cause the industries to flourish which in return lead to improve standard of living.* (Participant F, 2023).
 22. *Economic prosperity of the country is also depends upon the political stability which comes from literacy.* (Participant F, 2023).
 23. *Education of a country play a core part in economic prosperity.* (Participant F, 2023).
In the above sentences, there is an incorrect use of subject-verb agreement. There should be “has” instead of “have” to make proper verb tense agreement in the seventeenth sentence, “compels” in the eighteenth sentence, “makes” in the nineteenth sentence, “leads and advances” in the twentieth sentence, “causes and leads” in the twenty first sentence, “ is also depends” should be revised and retained as “also depends” in the twenty second sentence, and “plays” should be incorporated in the twenty third sentence respectively.
On the other hand, the below given sentences have errors in the article usage. There should be the use of the article “the” before “country”, “a” before “high”, and “a” before “political stability” in the given sentences. Moreover, in sentence number twenty seventh, “a” should be placed after “nutshell”, and “a” should also be paced before “high”.
 24. *GDP of country.* (Participant E, 2023).
 25. *If a country has high literacy rate.* (Participant F, 2023).
 26. *When people of any country are educated, there is political stability in that country.*

(Participant E, 2023).

27. *In nutshell, literacy rate affects the economy of country. With high literacy rate, economies of countries grow and show positive relation.* (Participant E, 2023).

Errors in the Noun Form Usage

Furthermore, the study also found noun form errors in the written excerpts of the CA students. For instance,

1. *The linked between economic prosperity of a nation and its level of literacy is undeniable.* (Participant C, 2023).

Here, the proper use of nouns is “link” to convey the proper sense and grammatical structure of the sentence.

Errors in Homophones Usage

The current research has identified errors in the use of homophone words. It is seen that CA students are unable to demarcate between the words with the same sounds but different spellings and meanings.

For example,

1. *Excess to better job opportunities and make informed financial decisions.* (Participant D, 2023).

In the above sentence, the proper use is “access” not “excess”. The usage here is incorrect by the participant.

Capitalization Errors

In addition, there are multiple errors of capitalization observed in the writings of the participants while conducting this research study. In English, words are supposed to be started from capital words at the start of the sentences and are not allowed to be capitalized somewhere in the middle of sentences. But it is observed that the majority of the CA students who participated in this research study as participants, were unaware of these basic English rules.

For example,

1. *furthermore*, at the very start of a sentence by (Participant D, 2023).
2. *Critics*, at the middle of the sentence by (Participant D, 2023).
3. *Literacy*, at the middle of the sentence by (Participant D, 2023).
4. *Education*, at the middle by (Participant B, 2023).

Errors in the Usage of Conjunctions, Adjectives and Prepositions

In the writing, conjunctions, adjectives and prepositions also hold significant importance to make proper phrasing and to bring clarity in the sentence. The study also identified errors in the usage of conjunctions, adjectives and prepositions by the CA students.

For example,

- *Education gives people knowledge and skills which they use and earn money.* (Participant E). In the sentence there should be “that” instead of “which” to make the syntactic structure of the sentence clear and understandable.
- *Contributes in the economy of that country.* (Participant E, 2023).
- *Seek for scientific explanation for everything.* (Participant F, 2023).
In the given sentences, the use of prepositions is incorrect by the participants. The revised version of the sentences should include “Contribute to”, and “of everything” to make grammatically correct use of a preposition.
- *If a country has high literacy rate, it not only lead to economical prosperity.* (Participant F, 2023).

In the given sentence, the adjective used by the participant is incorrect. It should be “economic” not “economical” as per the rules of adjectives.

After the thorough analysis of the written textual data, the study found multiple grammatical errors in the writings of CA students. They were in terms of punctuation and orthography, subject-verb agreement, adjectives, possessive pronouns, articles, capitalization, conjunctions, prepositions, homophones, and noun form usage. These are all grave errors in English, which are normally committed by the CA students. Therefore, they tend to fail in communicating their thoughts, when it comes to the academic context.

Content Organization and Argumentation

Every written task has its own pattern. The same notion applies to an argumentative essay. Basically, an argumentative essay is an essay in which different facts and figures are used to justify a claim or stance. It normally consists of a thesis statement that clarifies the stance of a writer and three claims, which are later supported with certain supportive arguments.

Moreover, in the academic context, adherence to the content organization, coherence and argumentation is mandatory to communicate thoughts in a logical manner, which leads to better academic performance. The research study found that the majority of the participants had adhered to the content organization of an argumentative essay and put forward logical arguments to validate their thesis statement. They clearly crafted their thesis statements and supported their stance with multiple arguments. For instance,

1. *Education is a key to success and helpful in the economic development of a nation. More the level of literacy, more it raise the economy. (Participant B, 2023).*
2. *Economic prosperity and literacy are interconnected aspect of nation. (Participant D, 2023).*

The above given sentences clearly manifest the stances of writers in their argumentative essays. The same notion has been followed by other participants to come up with logical flow and to legitimize their points of view or claims made in the thesis statements.

Moving on to the claims and supportive arguments, the study found that all the participants were aware of the pattern of an argumentative essay, and the requirement of forming multiple claims and supporting them with arguments. This shows that they were well enough exposed to the nature of writing an argumentative essay. It can be seen from the following paragraphs written by different participants.

For example,

1. *To begin with one can argue that a literate population forms the foundation for a skill workforce, driving innovation and productivity. Literacy empowers individual to participate more actively in the economy, making informed decisions and contributing to overall growth. (Participant D, 2023).*
2. *Economic prosperity of any nation depends upon the level of literacy in it. It is because literate people are well knowledgeable and trained to do their job with more efficiency and less wastage of resources. (Participant F, 2023).*

Here in the given paragraphs, the claims have been put forwarded with appropriate and logical transitions, which clearly manifests the comprehensive knowledge of the participants regarding presenting claims and supporting them with appropriate arguments in an argumentative essay.

On the other hand, the research study also came across a fact that some participants had no idea about proper coherence in the ideas, and its importance in validating the argumentative essay. The things they wrote in the essays were not in coherence to the topic as well as their thesis statements. This kind of thing has severe impact on the academic performance of students as they fail to satisfy the needs of an examiner and properly addressing a question

- For instance,
1. *Without education, success is impossible and education is the only key to success. So, we have to improve our education system that results in the economic development of a nation. There are many ways to improve education by giving free education to the students. It results in the availability of education to the students. (Participant B, 2023).*
 2. *When people of any country are educated, there is political stability in that country. There is no chaos and people know their rights in selection of political candidates and back them. (Participant E, 2023).*

Last but not the least, another important ingredient in any essay or argumentative essay is crafting a good conclusion. It is basically a summary of the arguments given in an argumentative essay. Conclusion cannot be excluded from any essay as it acts as an inevitable component, which gives insight to readers about claims, and what has been concluded based on them. In the given writing tasks, all the students were found to have written logical conclusions. The few instances of the conclusions can be seen below:

1. *In nutshell, literacy rate affects the economy of country. With high literacy rate, economies of countries grow and show positive relation. (Participant E, 2023).*

2. *In conclusion, the linked between the economic prosperity of a nation and its level of literacy is undeniable. A literate population serves as the engine of economic development, driving innovation, enhancing productivity, and reducing poverty. Investment in education is not just an investment in individuals but a strategic imperative for nations aspiring to thrive in the contemporary global landscape.* (Participant C, 2023).

In the above given examples, the participants can be seen to have incorporated conclusions. But the conclusion in sentence number one is not that comprehensive and summarizes the key points. However, the conclusion written by participant C has a summary of the key points given in the essay, which has made it a good academic conclusion. On the other hand, all the other participants have incorporated “conclusions” except participant A, where conclusion is not clarified in the written excerpt.

Findings

Based on comprehensive data analysis, this study finds that writing skills have an unlimited significance, and an important role in academic performance. Most of the exams are taken in written form, especially students must answer questions through long answer scripts in assignments or paper. They need to exhibit their writing skills to prove worthy of any academic achievement. Students with high and intermediate level of writing skills were found performing relatively better in their academics as compared to those who have had low level of writing skills as inferred from the given data analysis. A high level writing skills ensures good academic scores to students who can write through creativity and innovation. Students with low level of writing skills were found weak and thus, had academically poor performance.

Conclusion

The current study explored the connection between English writing proficiency and academic performance of the students of Chartered Accountancy (CA). It was concluded that English writing proficiency and academic performance are strongly connected. The results established the fact that English writing proficiency has an indirect impact on academic performance. This study has established the relation between the two variables. The research deduced that writing skills have had a considerable impact on the academic performance of the participants who were part of this study.

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